

The Impacts of Cavite Tourism's "TARA, CAVITE TAYO" Advertisement Video on the Travel Motivation of Prospective Tourists

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6565767>

Published Date: 20-May-2022

Abstract: The tourism advertisement has been used over the years to entice potential tourists to make their way to the United States for mostly recreational, holiday or other leisure activities. Tour package products and advertisements were now available on the different websites, video blog, or social media sites during this pandemic and now in an era of digital marketing. This study probed the impact of the "Tara, Cavite Tayo" video advertisement on the travel motivation among respondents and compared between demographic profiles. This shows that in all aspects using the AIDA Model of assessing a marketing strategy, there is very high agreement on the video advertising, which stimulates interest, leading to an action to travel to Cavite. This video advertisement can be studied in a variety of contexts and on social media platforms' space functions. The study also shows that there were no significant differences between their assessment by comparing among the demographic profile. This clearly shows that there is a great impact of this "Tara Tayo sa Cavite" Advertisement Video on the travel motivation of prospective tourists. Based on the results, this segment points several conclusions, that are pertinent to marketers or proprietors accommodations and leisure activities in tourism in the Province of Cavite.

Keywords: tourism, video advertisement, travel motivation, online tourism advertisement.

1. INTRODUCTION

The tourism industry is said to be a beacon of the national economy. This has been greatly affected by the onset of the pandemic. Different marketing and advertising adjustments have been made to be able to encourage local and international tourists to use social media. Tourism advertisement models were designed using video, printed posters, or even digital forms to attract visits to either historical or scenic places.

A slow pace of recovery is seen in the tourism industry. Although it has been noted that world tourism upturns by 4% in 2021, it remains far below pre-pandemic levels (United Nations World Tourism Organization, 2022). In 2020, a 73% decrease in international arrivals was recorded, and an insignificant increase in 2021 in overnight tourists, which was 72% below the pre-pandemic year. In the Philippines, domestic travel continued to increase in the last semester of 2021, but Filipinos were very prudent in their recreational tours (Philippine News Agency, 2021).

The province of Cavite is known for its historical and cultural heritage: churches, monuments, historical shrines, and food heritage like different cuisines of "pansit, bacalao, tamales, and kakanin" (Javellana, 2016). Both international and local tourists come to visit the province to see the different tourist attractions like "Bul kang Taal" from the vantage point of the city of Tagaytay and simply staycations for their family and friends to create happy memories.

Santiano (2018) claims that tourism is quite relevant in the local community. The sense of hospitality of the community is being shaped by tourism. A significant relationship between economic, social, and cultural activity and the local tourism industry is being created, as shown by the economic developments and job opportunities among the locals.

The provincial government of Cavite, through its Provincial Tourism Office, aims to ensure quality tourist experiences in the area to increase invitations for travel and leisure. The provincial tourism industry is encouraged to join in its "Accreditation on Wheels" collaborative project with the Department of Tourism (DOT).

The Philippine tourism laws promote economic growth, cultural awareness, and appreciation of biodiversity. The Republic Act 9593 declares a national policy for tourism, intended to increase investment in tourism, promote the workforce, and national development. In collaboration with local and national governments, the development and implementation of a national tourism action plan is underway. This will encourage competition in the tourism industry and maximize consumer choice. Local government units promote tourism-related activities and programs that raise awareness of tourism, protect the country's cultural diversity and heritage, and create a sense of historical and tourist culture among the general populace (Republic Act 9593, section 3b).

Significantly, local tourists failed to realize the abundant attractions and destinations in the province of Cavite. The rich historical, scenic, and cultural heritage is now advertised in different media platforms, whether printed, digital billboards, magazine articles, or on social media.

Trending on the onset of the pandemic are digital bookings and deal inquiries. Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube appeared to be effective marketing tools. Some establishments invested in the creation of websites to attract people's attention. Consumer satisfaction is now the focus of digital and online tourism advertisements. Watching an advertisement for a product or a specific location that may be visited because of the scenery is now being placed online by the travel sector, utilizing all aspects of social media. A notable example of a local tourism destination in the province is Café Agapita, which bakes family heritage bread and pastries, or Ilog Maria, a honeybee farm that produces natural products like soap, shampoo, and even lotion in Silang. Both examples utilized websites and social media marketing to attract tourists.

In a newspaper article, Talavera (2020) announced the launching of the Department of Tourism's Wake Up in PH promotional video in the pre-pandemic era. Its purpose is to continuously attract foreign investors to invest in the Philippines. The department also plans to launch new promotional material to be placed on international networks to revive interest, especially now that quarantine restrictions are eased out through the DOT's Branding and Marketing Communications Office (Philippine Star, 2020). These placed tourism advertisements as part of marketing and promotion intend to keep the Philippines as a top-of-mind tourism destination.

Background of the Study

Considering the economic impact on the tourism sector of the Province of Cavite during the COVID-19 pandemic, the blow of rippling opportunities to increase local tourism is its wave. Social media is currently used to disseminate news, updates, and events and promote the tourism of Cavite. The official Facebook page, created on September 8, 2011, has 29,526 likes and 34,431 followers, and the official Instagram has 476 followers. Building a long-term sustainability action plan in the aftermath of the pandemic's disastrous impact, both social and economic sustainability were emphasized through advertising of native delicacies, popular destinations, and cultural and historical heritage.

Advertising is one of the most effective ways of increasing tourists. Using media-driven platforms, this intangible product will persuade the consumer's choice through their imagination skills (Gurtoo, 2019). Lawson (2018) pointed out that to select a destination and attractions to visit, tourists seek information about the destination that is both interesting and useful, as well as traveler reviews.

Cavite is popularly acknowledged as a top-of-mind weekend getaway destination for Metro Manila dwellers. For decades, the blissful venue has served as a gathering spot for families and friends to stay connected and take a break from the busyness of daily life.

Cavite tourism's Tara Cavite Tayo was a short tourism video that showcased leisure parks, eco-tourism, food, accommodation, and historical sites in Cavite, and the video reached 17k likes, 1.8k comments, and 28k shares. In the video's comment section, a significant number of viewers are not aware that these places exist in Cavite. Viewers also commented and asked for information regarding the featured destination in the video. They also asked for the locations that are featured in the video, and many of them tagged their family and friends, encouraging them to peek at the video.

This shows the research gap regarding how the video impacts the travel motivation of prospective tourists, which was investigated in this paper.

The researchers also provided some factors for tourists' travel motivation. It is categorized into two types of travel motivation, which are the internal and external factors of tourist travel motivation. This explains why the internal factor influences a person's decision to travel whilst stimulating, going direct, and trying to integrate his behavior. While there are external factors in tourism, there are also external motives that can influence tourists and pull them towards a specific motivation and subsequent decision.

In these contexts, the respondents in this research were people living outside of the Cavite area, because they would likely want to know more about the tourist locations listed in the content of the Tara Cavite Tayo video. This would allow the researchers to provide more significant results as compared to selecting respondents inside Cavite.

Conceptual Framework

The Impacts of Cavite Tourism's "Tara Cavite Tayo" Advertisement Video on the Travel Motivation of Prospective Tourists

Figure 1: IPO Framework

This part points out the actions that the researchers followed in the completion of this study.

The first column of input shows the input of the study. The researchers would gather the personal data of the respondents for demographic profiling. The researchers would then proceed to assess the factors affecting the impact using the AIDA MODEL. The AIDA is a marketing effect model that describes the stages a consumer goes through when making a purchase decision. It includes direct and indirect material costs as well as service costs. Process-costing, on the other hand, can be used.

The second column of the process shows the process of conducting the study; the researchers would gather the data using Google forms and would apply the necessary statistical treatment before analyzing the gathered data.

Lastly, the third column for the output shows the output of the study. After applying the statistical treatments and analyzing the data, the researchers would suggest or propose recommendations.

Theoretical Framework

For many years, among the numerous models developed for assessing the effect of video advertisements on viewers, several advertisers have used Elmo Lewis's AIDA model Hierarchy of Effects Model to understand the various degrees of viewers' interaction with the advertisement, whether textual or visual, as well as the advertisement's effectiveness (Rehman et al., 2014).

Attention, interest, desire, and action are the acronyms for AIDA (Rehman et al., 2014). These are all the four stages through which a buyer, or in this case, a viewer, goes while visualizing or viewing an advertisement. (Rawal 2013). The initial purpose of advertising is to attract customers. After capturing the viewer's attention, an advertisement video must pique interest in the service and product, which in this case is the destination in the perception of the consumers. The advertisement must evoke the viewer's desire to use or obtain the product, and lastly, the viewer must decide whether to purchase the product, which in this case is deciding to visit the location.

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of this study is to provide an answer to these questions:

1. Identify the demographic profile of the prospective tourists based on the following dimensions listed below, and how do these demographic profiles affect their travel motivation?
 - 1.1 Gender
 - 1.2 Age
 - 1.3 Occupation
 - 1.4 Educational Attainment
 - 1.5 Civil Status
2. How are the travel motivations of the respondents affected based on their assessment of the marketing material using the AIDA Model?
 - 2.1 Awareness
 - 2.2 Interest
 - 2.3 Desire
 - 2.4 Action
3. Is there a significant difference in the respondents when individuals have been grouped by demographic profile?
4. As Stated in the results of the study, what suggestions and strategies that are needed to improve and increase the motivation of tourist to travel in Cavite?

Statement of Hypothesis:

There is no significant effect of tourism advertisement to the travel motivation of the prospective tourist and their demographic profile when grouped.

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

The scope and delimitations of this study focused on the relationship between the impacts of Cavite Tourism's "TARA, CAVITE TAYO" Advertisement Video on the Travel Motivation of Prospective Tourists that reside outside of Cavite. This study is limited by the interpretation of the selected participants, with respect to their acceptance of it, and it is too much affected, or it is good in travel motivation.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Cavite's Tourism

Cavite Province is the southern metropolitan province of Manila. The province is famous for its fields of history, culture, food, entertainment, and wellness. In 2013, the province received 1,775,531 foreign and domestic tourists. Most of these tourists visit Tagaytay City, while some tourists visit Kawit City. The proximity of the province to Metro Manila offers many visitors. On the other hand, the province is close to Metro Manila, on the other hand, and represents the largest tourist spot. (2016, Notorio, P., Jr., E., Desingano, B., Beunviaje, J., and Mejia, G.)

advertisement for tourism

Tourism advertising is dominated by the branding and platform used for the promotion of places, products, and other goods. In the 21st century, consumers rely heavily on online platforms, including for tourism advertisements.

Several studies have been conducted locally, but no assessment has been made with the Cavite Tourism advertisement in terms of the use of the AIDA Model and on the different demographics. In the tourism service industry, internet product advertising is perfect for gaining attention and generating interest among potential consumers. People are spending more and more of their leisure time on the internet, which allows them to learn about events in other countries, plan forthcoming holidays, and pay for them all with just a few clicks without ever leaving their homes

Fotis (2015) studied the use of social media and its impacts on consumer behavior. The study contributes to holiday travel related social media research by identifying six major functions of social media during active users' holiday travel process (section 10.2): (1) Inspiration; (2) Collaboration; (3) Decision making; (4) Self-expression; (5) Communication; and (6) Entertainment. These functions are proposed as spaces within the holiday travel process that enclose active users' specific behaviors and cognitive functions. The social media functional spaces share three properties that characterize their position and shape within the holiday travel process: fluidity, extension, and overlap. The six functional spaces provide a conceptual framework for the overall usage of social media in each of the stages of the travel process, as well as in each of the stages of the decision-making process, so as to enable researchers to focus at a micro level.

Travel Motivation through Tourism Advertising

Travel motivation is the primary reason for traveling behavior, and it is critical for understanding tourists' decision-making processes as well as evaluating the subsequent satisfaction of tourists' expectations. (Wall and Mathieson, as quoted by Njagi et al., 2017).

This could be explained by the relationship between the motivation of the tourist and his memorability of the tourist destinations. Tourism attributes are shaped by a series of destinations and are influenced by specific or internal factors like personal characteristics, motivations, perceptions, opinions, product preferences, and understanding. The attributes of tourist destinations are still accumulating from various memorable tourism experiences (Kim and Chen, 2016).

According to Fesenmaier (2017), advertising effects in tourism have generally been defined as consumers' responses to advertisements, which has been widely accepted by researchers. Aside from behavioral and cognitive factors, a few affective variables were used to assess the effects of tourism advertisements in previous papers, such as people's desire and interest in specific locations, as well as their willingness to travel. According to existing tourism literature, the impact of tourism advertising has been quantified using a variety of variables, including tourism's behavioral, cognitive, and affective dimensions. Several variables to consider include awareness, the usefulness of travel information, attitude, interest, desire, credibility, and behavioral intention. (Christianian, 2016; Li, Huang, & Christianian, 2016).

Destination marketing is a type of marketing that focuses on increasing the number of tourists at a particular destination. According to Promodo (2018), What is tourism marketing, according to the article? Destination marketing is the type of

tourism promotion that focuses on a particular location. Destination marketing employs social media, commercials, and other marketing strategies. To promote a destination, advertisements and even tourist stories are used.

According to Otto et al. (2016) Age, gender, occupation, education level, income level, and other sociodemographic characteristics all have a significant impact on travel preferences and behavior. Meng and Uysal (2008), as quoted by SO (2020), stated that single visitors are more likely than married visitors to seek out adventure activities in their destination of choice in the study of Xuea & Zhangb, as quoted by Wu & Cai, (2020). They used three groups: local tourists, short-distance tourists, and long-distance tourists, and the behavioral distinctions between the three groups indicate that their trips were motivated by different interests. Results show that local visitors came for shopping and relaxation, while tourists who are considered short haul came for relaxation and sight-seeing, and lastly, tourists who are considered long-haul came solely for sight-seeing.

AIDA Model

The AIDA Model indicates the cognitive stages that a consumer undergoes when making a purchase. It is a purchasing funnel in which buyers progress through stages to make the final purchase. (2021 Hanlon) These are the phases that a viewer experiences when watching an advertisement. Advertising's primary goal is to attract customers. Rawal (as cited by Fong et al., 2017).

Practicing the four phases of the AIDA MODEL, researchers will form questions in these four phases for our research question number two. The AIDA model will be used as a device to include the impacts of the tourism advertisement video "TARA CAVITE TAYO." And define whether the video has a meaningful and notable set of outcomes on the proposed tourist's travel impulse.

3. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study will generate quantitative research in which it will concentrate on statistical data that is relevant to the research topic. Quantitative research is a type of research that collects and analyzes numerical data to determine relationships, patterns, and effects between variables using statistical methods. This type of research collects numerical data using questionnaires or surveys. It will discuss its relationship to prospective tourists' travel motivations and the impact of tourism advertisement videos. The study would use a four-point Likert scale to rank people's perceptions on a scale of low to high. The data collected from respondents will be used to determine the impact of Cavite Tourism's "TARA CAVITE TAYO" on the travel motivation of prospective tourists, which will serve as the basis for suggestions and recommendations.

The study will conduct the research using a descriptive survey method. Descriptive research is a type of research that focuses on the current state of the subject of the study. Descriptive research is a type of research that is used to explain or characterize the characteristics of the population under investigation. It is a study that was designed to evaluate accurate information from respondents. The researchers would let the respondents included in the study use the experiences of the prospective tourists as a basis in answering the questionnaire.

Sampling Method

The researchers used a Purposive Sampling Using a purposive sampling, sample members from a larger population are selected based on their Perception about the used tourism advertisement and the objective of the study. Under the purposive sampling the researchers will select a group of people having a shared Perception about the used tourism advertisement.

The selected population of the researchers for this study is the selected people who are not a resident of Cavite. The researchers needed 258 individuals, The researchers will ensure that all gathered information will be kept confidential and will be used for education purposes only.

Research Locale

The study will be conducted in all social media platform available since we are in a state of pandemic. Social media is the handiest tools in this new normal set up.

Sampling Size

$$S_s = \frac{NV + [Se^2 \times (1-p)]}{Nse + [\sqrt{2} \times p(1-p)]}$$

The researchers will use scientific sampling under unrestricted random sampling. Meaning there is no limitations; every member of the population has an equal chance of being included in the sample.

Below is the computation on how the researchers compute for the total population of respondents.

$$= \frac{14,158,573(2.58) + [0.01^2 \times (1 - 0.50)]}{14,158,573(0.01) + [2.58^2 \times 0.50(1 - 0.50)]}$$

$$= \frac{36,529,118.34 + 0.01^2 \times (0.50)}{94,254,125.137 + 2.58^2 \times 0.50(0.50)}$$

$$= \frac{18,264,559.17}{23,563,531.309}$$

Total sampling size = 258.00 or 258.0019676

Participants of the study

The Participants of the study will be the people living outside of Cavite. such as laguna, Batangas, Quezon, Rizal, and Metro manila. The respondents will be 258. the requirements to be able to be a respondent is they should be living outside of Cavite. The instrument that will be used by the researchers is a survey using Google Forms with a Likert scale format.

Data Gathering

The researchers would use the online platform to collect all the data for the study. The researchers intended to use Google Forms exclusively to distribute their survey questionnaires to respondents. Researchers would employ the four-point Likert scale in the construction of their research survey questionnaires to extract specific responses from the respondents.

Using the four phases of AIDA MODEL, researchers will formulate questions in these four phases for

Data Treatment and Analysis

The researchers will use frequency and percentage distribution to organize and group the respondents according to the category to which they belong. The mean will also be used in this study. Another statistical treatment that the researchers will be using is ANOVA to determine the connection between two or more groups in the study.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This shows the outcome of the gathered data and the demographic profile of the respondents regarding their age, gender, civil status, occupation, and educational attainment.

1. Identify the demographic profile of the prospective tourists based on the following dimensions listed below, and how do these demographic profiles affect their travel motivation?

1.1 Age

AGE	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Rank
18 y/o and below	16	6.202	6.202	6.202	4
19-28 y/o	169	65.504	65.504	71.705	1
29 - 38 y/o	46	17.828	17.829	89.535	2
30 y/o & above	27	10.465	10.465	100	3
Total	258	100			

Figure 2: Demographics Profile according to Age

The figure shows that 66.5% among the respondents are 19 to 24 years old and only 6.3% of the total respondents are youth. As stated on the table above it shows that majority of the viewers are young adults. The highest rank is 19 – 28 years old which means that these viewers are active in social media watching this kind of advertisement videos. This shows that this age group is the main online market who are prevalent in its use of the technology (Pataganao, 2020).

While the lowest rank is 18 and below is because they are more on playing online games rather than to watch video advertisement online.

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Rank
Male	119	46.124	46.124	46.124	2
Female	123	47.674	47.674	93.798	1
LGBTQ	16	6.202	6.202	100	3
Total	258	100			

Figure 3: Demographics Profile according to Gender

The figure 3 shows the gender dynamics among the respondents, a slight difference among the number of respondents between female (47.2%) and male (46.1%). The table presented that the highest percentage which emphasizes that female with 47.2% because women tend to enjoy adventures and travel. While the lowest rank is the LGBTQ community that has a 6.20 percent states that they are more likely interest in physical activities like volleyball. They are also more aware when it comes to political views.

This implies in an exploratory study, Hamid, et. al. (2021) considerably concluded that the solo travelers are women to bring positive change on the well-being.

Civil Status	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Rank
Single	225	87.209	87.209	87.209	1
Married	26	10.078	10.078	97.287	2
Widowed	3	1.163	1.163	98.45	3
Divorced	2	0.775	0.775	99.225	4
In a relationship	2	0.775	0.775	100	5
Total	258	100			

Figure 4: Demographics Profile according to Civil Status

The figure 4 shows the that a most of the respondents are singles, around 87.7% of the entire respondents and only 9.7% are married. Other relationship status was taken into considerations.

This simply means that all the respondents who are single receives the highest, since they spend most of their free time browsing on the internet on their phones, laptops etc. With the lowest rank, married is because they tend to prioritize their family's needs.

In a study to produce attractive travel packages in can be noted that singles are the most potential market (Matosic, 2017).

Occupation	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Rank
Student	173	67.054	67.054	67.054	1
Professional	23	8.915	8.915	75.969	3
Private Employee	48	18.605	18.605	94.574	2
Others	14	5.426	5.426	100	4
Total	258	100			

Figure 5: Demographics Profile according to Occupation

It is notable in figure 5 that most of the respondents are students (67.7%), professionals are 8.9% and private employees are 18.2%. Whereas the students have the highest rank among the two variables since they are less likely to have responsibilities and have more time compared to the private employee and professional.

(Sigala,2017 Dolan et al., 2016) as more study has been dedicated to the benefits of consumer participation and engagement in value co-creation via social media.

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Rank
Basic Education	43	16.667	16.667	16.667	4
Higher Education	53	20.543	20.543	37.209	3
Bachelor's Degree	68	26.357	26.357	63.566	2
Master's Degree	1	0.388	0.388	63.953	7
Undergraduate	83	32.171	32.171	96.124	1
Postgraduate	4	1.55	1.55	97.674	6
Others	6	2.326	2.326	100	5
Total	258	100			

Figure 6: Demographics Profile according to Educational Attainment

The figure 6 shows that 46.8% are both college or bachelor's degree holders, 32.3% among the respondents are undergraduate or college level, and 1.4% are with graduate degrees.

As states in the results of the table undergraduates are among the highest percentage that has a 32.171% which implies that when they travel, they learn new things, strategy and the lifestyle of the residents who live there, they are also curious with what's with the place. With lowest rank, is post graduate is because they tend to focus on their career.

Ahmad (2019) pointed out that there is a relationship of educational attainment on the travel choices for recreational purposes.

2.How are the travel motivations of the respondents affected based on their assessment of the marketing material using the AIDA Model?

Table 1: Travel Motivation Awareness

Travel Motivation: Awareness	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Q1.1	1.337	strongly Agree
Q1.2	1.38	strongly Agree
Q1.3	1.306	strongly Agree
Q1.4	1.271	strongly Agree
Q1.5	1.341	strongly Agree
Q1.6	1.314	strongly Agree
Q1.7	1.298	strongly Agree
Q1.8	1.322	strongly Agree
Overall Level of travel motivation in terms of awareness	1.321	Very High

The table 1 shows that using AIDA Model of Travel Advertisement assessment, all the items asked for the awareness aspects are strongly agree.

As Stated in the table above A lot of respondents were aware of the information said in the video. It captures the audience attention.

The overall level of travel motivation in terms of awareness is very high to attract the attention of the customers. Can (2020), identified the positive influence of the travel webpage, flyers, or other media marketing on the decisions of travel of clients. The awareness of a travel destination using this model is mostly influences by the quality of the advertisement video if it is catching cinematography, clear message and vibrant.

Table 2: Travel Motivation Interest

Travel Motivation: Interest	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Q2.1	1.337	strongly Agree
Q2.2	1.295	strongly Agree
Q2.3	1.287	strongly Agree
Q2.4	1.384	strongly Agree
Q2.5	1.434	strongly Agree
Q2.6	1.337	strongly Agree
Q2.7	1.411	strongly Agree
Q2.8	1.341	strongly Agree
Overall Level of travel motivation in terms of interest	1.353	Very High

On the determination if the advertisement of the marketing video boosts the interest's potential of the clients, Table 2 would show that all aspects have strongly agree responses, and very high overall level of travel motivation in terms of interest. It can be noted that it reflects on the interest of the customer's increased understanding of history of Cavite, featured sceneries and the products advertised.

As seen in the table above, the video has captured the interest of many viewers, because of the featured places in video they wanted are curious of what the places looks like, and they wanted to travel there to experience the fun in what the video is showing.

The advertising effect ignites interests of the potential leisure travels among target markets and correct individuation will clearly satisfy the expectations of the clientele (Pataganao, et al., 2020).

Table 3: Travel Motivation Desire

Travel Motivation: desire	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Q3.1	1.384	strongly Agree
Q3.2	1.395	strongly Agree
Q3.3	1.446	strongly Agree
Q3.4	1.391	strongly Agree
Q3.5	1.322	strongly Agree
Q3.6	1.36	strongly Agree
Q3.7	1.26	strongly Agree
Q3.8	1.453	strongly Agree
Overall Level of travel motivation in terms of desire	1.376	Very High

The table 3 the strongly agree of all the items on these aspects moves the mindset among the target market to desire to like it or want it (CFI, 2019). The overall level of travel motivation in terms of desire is 1.376 which can be interpreted as very high. The respondents tend to like to eat the delicacies of Cavite or like to try the activities included in the video advertisement.

Supporting to these results, singles in Finland usually book their travels through holidays through internet web pages or in social media sites, as a product of their desires after the marketing tools online or in television about tourist destinations or tour packages (Matosic, 2017). Although in his study, he pointed out that the singles in his study preferred to travel with other singles or families.

In this aspect, it is evident that there was a positive effect of changing the perspective of the tourism destination among the different destinations in Cavite. The viewers having desire to travel to the feature places in the viewers means that the advertisement video is effective.

Table 4: Travel Motivation Action

Travel Motivation: action	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Q4.1	1.38	strongly Agree
Q4.2	1.442	strongly Agree
Q4.3	1.477	strongly Agree
Q4.4	1.43	strongly Agree
Q4.5	1.388	strongly Agree
Q4.6	1.508	strongly Agree
Q4.7	1.368	strongly Agree
Q4.8	1.38	strongly Agree
Overall Level of travel motivation in terms of action	1.422	Very High

As geared by the last step of the AIDA model, the target clients must make an action based on the desire of change mindset caused by the advertisement. The table 4, shows that the respondents strongly agree to try the featured products in the tourism advertisement video. The overall level of travel motivation in terms of action is 1.422 which is very high. In the digital marketing era, the clients were perceived to pass through the stages in the AIDA Model prior to making an action (Heintz, 2021). Although there are still subsequent factors in the equation of the action made of the clients from a certain advertisement, this study would prove that setting into an action are results of the advertising effect especially audio-visual advertisement.

Since the viewers are strongly agreeing to go to their desired places featured in the video it means that the advertisement video has an impact to the viewers especially if the viewer loves to go to places.

This study proves that the AIDA model remains applicable even in a digital society. Consequently, target markets assessment and evaluation of video advertisement are products a process. Since the AIDA model was founded, both consumer and advertising consumption habits have evolved tremendously. in 1898 (Heintz, 2021). Critics of the AIDA model point to the following, among other things, as reasons for its lack of application to everyday digital business: "A major reason for this is that the customer journey has gotten increasingly complicated amid the expanding digital transition." "Purchasing decisions are rarely so straightforward. The order in which advertising impacts appear changes from time to time. In the case of specific adverts, such as those displayed after entering a search query in Search engines such as google, "interest" does not necessarily follow "attention," but typically does.

3. Is there a significant difference in the assessment of the respondents when grouped by demographic profile?

Table 5: Comparison by Age

Age	Awareness	interest	desire	action	overall
18 and below	1.297	1.43	1.391	1.461	1.395
19-24	1.353	1.388	1.433	1.463	1.409
25 to 30	1.283	1.264	1.207	1.31	1.266
above 30	1.204	1.245	1.306	1.329	1.271
F-value	0.881	1.346	2.571	1.236	1.517
p-value	0.451	0.26	0.055	0.297	0.21

There is no significant difference in the assessment of the marketing material using the AIDA Model, specifically, awareness, interest, desire, and action when grouped by age since the F-values of 0.881, 1.346, 2.571 and 1.236 have p-values greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference was not rejected. This indicated that the assessment of the marketing material in respect of interest, awareness, desire, and action is the same across all age groups. Philipps and Stanton (2019) recalled that young adult market are the trendsetters. Mature costumers becoming more critical in their choices of products.

Moreover, there is no significant difference in the overall assessment of the marketing material using the AIDA Model, when they are organized by age, since the F-value of 1.517 has a p-value greater than 0.05. The no significant difference null hypothesis was not rejected. This indicated that the overall assessment of the marketing material is the same across all age groups.

Table 6: Comparison by Gender

GENDER	Awareness	interest	desire	action	overall
Male	1.29	1.289	1.328	1.341	1.312
Female	1.345	1.41	1.409	1.491	1.413
LGBTQ	1.375	1.398	1.492	1.484	1.438
F-value	0.489	1.899	1.181	2.361	1.549
p-value	0.614	0.152	0.309	0.096	0.215

There is no significant difference in the assessment of the marketing material using the AIDA Model, specifically, awareness, interest, desire, and action F-values of 0.489, 1.899, 1.181, and 2.631 have p-values greater than 0.05 when grouped by gender. The no significant difference null hypothesis was not rejected. This indicated that respondents with different gender have the same assessment of the marketing material in terms of awareness, interest, desire, and action. Although this study contrasts with Johnson (2021), where women have more complex choices than men due to their brain functions and processes.

Also, Since the F-value of 1.549 has a p-value greater than 0.05, there is no significant difference in the overall assessment of the marketing material using the AIDA Model when grouped by gender. The null hypothesis of no significant difference was not rejected. This indicated that respondents with different gender have the same overall assessment of the marketing material.

Table 7: Comparison by Civil Status

CIVIL STATUS	Awareness	interest	desire	action	overall
Single	1.345	1.372	1.402	1.45	1.392
Marries	1.163	1.245	1.188	1.24	1.209
Others	1.143	1.143	1.25	1.179	1.179
F-value	2.149	1.434	2.273	2.412	2.303
p-value	0.119	0.24	0.105	0.092	0.102

Since the F-values of 2.149, 1.434, 2.273, and 2.412 have p-values greater than 0.05, there is no significant difference in the assessment of marketing material using the AIDA Model, specifically, awareness, interest, desire, and action when grouped by civil status. The null hypothesis of no significant difference was not rejected. This indicated that respondents with different civil status have the same assessment of the marketing material in terms of awareness, interest, desire, and action. Matosic (2017) would somehow support to these results although, regardless of civil status product review can be a new trend in social media marketing.

Also, Since the F-value of 2.303 has a p-value greater than 0.05, there is no significant difference in the overall assessment of the marketing material using the AIDA Model when grouped by civil status. The null hypothesis of no significant difference was not rejected. This indicated that respondents with different civil status have the same overall assessment of the marketing material.

Table 8: Comparison by Occupation

OCCUPATION	Awareness	interest	desire	action	overall
STUDENT	1.359	1.409	1.446	1.484	1.424
PROFESSIONAL	1.255	1.321	1.261	1.375	1.303
PRIVATE EMPLOYEE	1.188	1.193	1.185	1.237	1.201
OTHERS	1.42	1.268	1.366	1.357	1.353
F-value	1.932	2.659	3.779	2.71	2.987
p-value	0.125	0.049	0.011	0.046	0.032

Since the F-value of 1.932 has a p-value greater than 0.05, there is no significant difference in the assessment of marketing material using the AIDA Model, specifically, awareness when grouped by occupation. The no significant difference null hypothesis was not rejected. This indicated that respondents with different occupations have the same assessment of the marketing material in terms of awareness. Worldstram (2020), similarly would show that occupation does not affect on the assessment of the clients to a certain advertisement, they tend to become mature, critical, and careful due to educational qualifications also.

However, Since the F-values of 2.659, 3.779, and 2.71 have p-values less than 0.05, there is a significant difference in the assessment of marketing material using the AIDA Model, specifically, interest, desire, and action when grouped by occupation. The no significant difference null hypothesis was rejected. This indicated that the student's lowest assessment of the marketing material in terms of interest, desire, and action while private employees gave the highest assessment.

Also Since the F-value of 2.987 has a p-value less than 0.05, there is a significant difference in the overall assessment of the marketing material using the AIDA Model when grouped by occupation. The no significant difference null hypothesis was rejected. This indicated that students gave the lowest and private employees gave the highest overall assessment of the marketing material.

Table 9: Comparison by Educational Attainment

EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT	Awareness	interest	desire	action	overall
Basic education	1.419	1.468	1.483	1.567	1.484
Bachelor's Degree/ College Graduate	1.246	1.294	1.303	1.353	1.299
Others	1.374	1.376	1.423	1.443	1.404
F-value	2.935	2.15	2.576	2.523	2.833
p-value	0.055	0.119	0.078	0.082	0.061

Since the F-values of 2.935, 2.15, 2.576, and 2.523 have p-values greater than 0.05, there is no significant difference in the assessment of marketing material using the AIDA Model, specifically, awareness, interest, desire, and action when grouped by educational attainment. The no significant difference null hypothesis was not rejected. This indicated that respondents with different educational attainment have the same assessment of the marketing material in terms of awareness, interest, desire, and action.

Also, Since the F-value of 2.833 has a p-value greater than 0.05, there is no significant difference in the overall assessment of the marketing material using the AIDA Model when grouped by educational attainment. The no significant difference null hypothesis was not rejected. This indicated that respondents with different educational attainment have the same overall assessment of the marketing material.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The study was able to gather information of the different travel motivations among the respondents in terms of the demographic profile, mostly single young adults were the respondents who have at least a college level education. Basing on their assessment of the video advertisement it shows a strong agreement on the effect on their travel motivations in terms of the use of AIDA Model (Awareness, Interest, Desire, and Action). The results show a very high level in all aspects of the advertisement.

The study also shows that there were no significant differences between their assessment by comparing among the demographic profile. This clearly shows that there is a great impact of this “Tara Tayo sa Cavite” Advertisement Video on the travel motivation of prospective tourists.

The figure shows that 66.5% among the respondents are 19 to 24 years old and only 6.3% of the total respondents are youth. The highest rank is 19 – 28 years old which means that these viewers are active in social media watching this kind of advertisement videos.

The gender dynamics among the respondents, a slight difference among the number of respondents between female (47.2%) and male (46.1%). The table presented that the highest percentage which emphasizes that female with 47.2% because women tend to enjoy adventures and travel.

The figure 4 shows that a most of the respondents are singles, around 87.7% of the entire respondents. This simply means that all the respondents who are single receive the highest, since they spend most of their free time browsing on the internet on their phones, laptops etc.

It is notable in figure 5 that most of the respondents are students (67.7%), Whereas the students have the highest rank among the two variables since they are less likely to have responsibilities and have more time compared to the private employee and professional.

As states in the results of the table undergraduates are among the highest percentage that has a 32.171%

The researchers identified the positive influence of the travel webpage, flyers, or other media marketing on the decisions of travel of clients. The awareness of a travel destination using this model is mostly influenced by the quality of the advertisement video if it is catching cinematography, clear message and vibrant.

With the table above shows that the video advertisement is interesting to watch because of the featured places and how the actors in the video really had an appeal to the viewers.

Stated the table above can see that the respondents strongly agree to go to the featured places in the video. They are curious to what can they expect when they go there and what services that place can offer, and to know if it is worth it to go there.

Since the result in the table above came out strongly agree, it means that the video had an impact to the respondents who watched the video about Cavite.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, this section identifies several implications, which are relevant to marketers or proprietors of tourism accommodations and leisure activities in the Province of Cavite.

Marketers seek insights and understanding of consumers' behavior to formulate effective and efficient marketing strategies and actions in this digital era. Vlogs, social media reviews and online social media reach. TV advertisements may still be necessary, but web connectivity would be more efficient. The findings of this study suggest that:

1. Respondents interact with a video advertisement and via social media throughout all four stages of the assessment process.
2. Interactions with and via social media take place throughout all stages of AIDA Model Assessment but could be studied through different holidays in a year.
3. Throughout assessment using AIDA Model, it should have been studied also on the six functional spaces that incorporate social media related cognitive and behavioral functions on video advertisement and not only among demographics.
4. The lowest ranked are those aged 18 and under, who prefer to play online games rather than watch commercials. As a result, the researcher will suggest that characters be included in the advertising film to entice fans of online games to watch the commercial.
5. The LGBTQ community has the lowest ranking because they favor physical sports such as volleyball. As a result, the researcher suggested that they show physical activities for people who enjoy exercising to increase the number of LGBTQ.
6. The married have the lowest ranking since they are busier with their families than the singles. As a result, the researcher suggested that the video advertisements be combined with family bonding to persuade the family to watch the promotional video and visit these locations.
7. Professionals and private employees have the lowest rank because professionals and private employees have greater duties than students. As a result, the researcher suggested that they provide spaces where professionals and private employees can unwind.
8. undergraduate receives the highest percentage because they are less likely to have responsibilities and have more time compared to the private employee and professional. The research suggest that they can suggest it to their schools that these places can be an itinerary when they have a fieldtrip. They will have fun and learn many things.
9. To be able to improve the awareness of the AIDA model, the researchers suggest, should look for different sources of information rather than sticking to the AIDA model because there are many other theories outside the AIDA model.
10. the researchers suggest, providing a short clip about the history of Cavite in detail to entice people to watch the ads.
11. the researchers suggest, Displays all the delicacies accessible in Cavite, as well as the path to the various destinations.
12. Lasty, the researchers suggest, hopefully they make yet another video for people who liked their video advertisement.

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